

CERTIFICATE

of participation

3060-4737

Synapses: insights across the disciplines

The certificate is presented to

Umida Oralbayeva

For publication of the research article

**Theme: " IZZET QIZ " DÁSTANI TILINDE REŃ BILDIRIWSHI
FRAZEOLOGIZMLERDIŃ QOLLANILIW ÓZGESHELIKLERI**

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF
Eshkaraev S.CH

07.01.2026

Date

Research Science and
Innovation House

